

DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC AND CREATIVE COMPETENCES OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS

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Methodology

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Abstract. *This article deals with the problems of improving the methodology of developing the scientific and creative competencies of the future primary school teacher. Also, in the article, a formative method for improving the development of scientific and creative competences of future elementary school teachers, as well as the analysis of the fundamental views and theories of several foreign and our republic's pedagogic scientists were also considered. Scientific-creative approach, competence approach, the concepts of competence were explained in detail by the author, and this topic was analyzed from a pedagogical and psychological point of view.*

Keywords: *competence, scientific, creative approach, method, psychology, education, training, teacher, student, theory.*

INTRODUCTION. The scientific and creative competence of a future teacher is his constant search for answers to the questions "why?" and "how to do it better?" This process is carried out systematically on the basis of modern curricula developed by the Educational and Methodological Departments of higher educational institutions. The thoughts of the President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, "It is extremely important to solve another problem: this is the professional level of the teaching staff and professors, their special knowledge. In this regard, it is necessary to create an environment that actively supports the processes of obtaining education, spiritual and educational maturity, and the formation of true values, are of great importance. [1, 45-b]

The individual trajectory of independent educational activity of each teacher, who is a participant in the formative experience of improving the methodology for developing the scientific and creative competencies of a future primary school teacher, is formed from the starting point, which occurs in self-knowledge, when the work of identifying the need for scientific and creative activity is carried out, to the level of involvement in scientific and creative activity and self-organization for scientific and creative formation. From a psychological point of view, there is no significant difference between the scientific and creative activity of a scientist who discovers objective new laws of the surrounding world that are not yet known to humanity, and the productive thinking of a teacher who discovers new things only for himself, since they are based on psychic laws. Therefore, in the experiment, forms, methods, and tools of independent educational activity of future primary school teachers are selected that are similar to those available to future primary school teachers.

METHODS. The individual trajectory of independent educational activity of each teacher participating in the formative experiment on the development of scientific and creative competence of future primary school teachers is organized from the starting point of self-knowledge, the identification of the need for scientific and creative activity, to the level of involvement in scientific and creative activity and self-organization for scientific and creative formation.

From a psychological point of view, there is no significant difference between the scientific and creative activity of a scientist who discovers new objective laws of the surrounding world that are still unknown to humanity, and the productive thinking of a teacher who discovers new things only for himself, because the basis of both is psychological laws. For this reason, in the experiment, forms, methods, and tools of independent learning activities of future primary school teachers were selected that were similar to those available to future primary school teachers. However, just as the level of intellectual activity that leads to discovery varies, the conditions under which they discover new knowledge also vary. In order to clarify such differences, most researchers prefer to call such activities of schoolchildren "productive activity", and use the term "scientific and creative activity" to understand the highest level of intellectual activity of individuals who discover something fundamentally new, unique, original for human knowledge.

Competence - the Latin word "Competentia", the dictionary meaning of which in Uzbek is "a person who knows well", "has experience". Competence - the ability to do something effectively, the ability to meet the requirements of the job, the ability to meet the requirements of performing specific work functions [5]. Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for the implementation of professional activities by a specialist and their high level of practical application. L.M. Mitina understood pedagogical competence as a harmonious combination of knowledge about the subject, teaching methodology and didactics, pedagogical communication skills and competence, as well as methods and means of self-development, self-improvement, self-realization. He distinguished the following three components in the structure of pedagogical competence: active, communicative and personal.

Creativity is manifested in the teacher's creativity, which determines the educational content of his professional activity, independent activity in the process of his work [3]. Creativity is a process that creates qualitatively new, original and unique scientific innovations in the process of teacher education. Any problem set in the productive creativity of the teacher is successfully solved, these aspects are manifested in the majority of teachers who are capable of creativity [5]. The teacher's heuristic creativity means the bold assimilation and promotion of innovations in professional activity taking place in the world, that is, the intensification of the formation of ideas, hypotheses on its basis and the consistent implementation of their closeness to reality, probability, reliability, and the ability to act boldly in a new situation, the development of thinking based on the process of thinking is observed. The teacher's creative creativity is embodied in the creation of new theories of social significance, he comes up with his own independent ideas and proposals, only skilled and experienced, qualified teachers can achieve this [4].

European sociologists call the positive state of a teacher's work "feeling the flow", that is, being completely immersed in their work and getting satisfaction from the process of work, which, in turn, testifies to the high internal reflexive state of the teacher [5]. The work of teachers who do not feel creativity and satisfaction from their work in the process of their profession often leads to inaction, rapid nervous exhaustion and irritability. The development of scientific and creative competence of future primary school teachers requires the inclusion of scientific and creative tasks, non-standard situations and the corresponding forms, methods and means in independent educational activities. Professional scientific and creative needs and motivation play an important role in the development of scientific and creative competence of future primary school teachers. The nature of scientific and creative activity; The direct participation of teachers in the selection of non-standard tasks, the use of situations that are important for the individual in which the value-motivational, constructive and reflexive-purposeful components of the scientific and creative

competence of future primary school teachers are updated, are considered to be determining factors for the development of the scientific and creative competence of primary school teachers.

RESULTS. We will consider in more detail the stages of the technology for developing the scientific and creative competence of future primary school teachers.

- At the first - diagnostic stage, the educational institution psychologist works with teachers who have expressed a desire to participate in the creative workshop (experimental group) and a group of volunteer teachers from primary schools (control group) and identifies the initial level of development of the scientific and creative competence of future primary school teachers and the existing conditions for its development. Diagnosis makes it possible to establish whether the phenomenon under study meets certain standards and criteria.

In the process of diagnosing and assessing the level of development of the initial scientific and creative competence of future primary school teachers, the pedagogical conditions necessary for optimizing the process of developing the scientific and creative competence of future primary school teachers are identified and clarified; the features of the development of scientific and creative activity and its individual psychological and pedagogical mechanisms are studied. In particular, the diagnostic information obtained at this stage serves as "input" information for the subsequent design phase. The purpose of the diagnostic stage is to develop the need for the development of scientific and creative competence of future primary school teachers. At this stage, the practice of analyzing and sharing experience with colleagues is carried out. At the first stage, priority is given to partial-search methods, which involve partially explaining new ideas by setting problems and tasks; Problematic situations are created in the educational and cognitive work of the participants of the creative workshop.

A skilled teacher conducts self-analysis and notes professional difficulties that arise in the activities of the workshop participants. Based on the results of the work, all participants of the workshop, including the master teacher, develop an individual educational path or an individual plan for independent learning to overcome professional difficulties, taking into account the results of the diagnosis, needs, abilities, and level of readiness for independent scientific and creative activity. This technology places a special emphasis on the development of independent learning activities, independent goal setting, plans, strategies, and self-assessment criteria. First, each teacher applies the experience of a master teacher in practice, studies the tested examples and standards described in methodological works and recommendations, uses two-way communication, adjusts his actions based on the results, and works on the basis of "methodical application", "template" and the experience of a master teacher. After that, the teacher proceeds to the task of finding something new: either for himself, innovative non-standard ways of solving pedagogical problems, or for himself and others, creating and finding original approaches, individual methods that recreate a certain pedagogical experience.

The novelty of the problem requires the use of new methods, such as the introduction of leaps and bounds, heuristics, search patterns, the increased role of semantics, and the content analysis of the problem. In this process, along with verbal-logical, well-understood generalizations, intuitive-practical generalizations that initially did not find their corresponding counterpart in the word are very important. They arise in the process of analyzing simulated situations, solving concrete practical problems, and analyzing real actions with objects or their models. This facilitates the search for the unknown, but this search process is carried out outside the clear sphere of consciousness, in an intuitive manner. The first stage is characterized by a positive attitude towards knowledge and the systematic and independent satisfaction of the

scientific and creative need for knowledge, which arises in the absence of an integrated independent educational technology, based on the situation.

DISCUSSION. The development of scientific and creative competencies of future primary school teachers is one of the priority tasks of the modern education system. This process involves the formation of not only teaching skills in students, but also the ability to create new pedagogical ideas and find creative solutions to problems.

The main areas of development of this competency are as follows:

1. Orientation to scientific and research activities

It is important to involve students in small scientific research from their student years.

Coursework and graduation qualification works: Orientation of topics not only to theoretical, but also to real problems in school practice.

Scientific circles: Cultivation of analytical thinking through circles such as "Young Pedagogue", "Creative Teacher".

2. Formation of creativity and creative approach

A primary school student understands the world through games and images. Therefore, the teacher:

Pedagogical innovations: Mastering non-traditional teaching methods (case studies, project-based learning, STEAM technologies).

Design thinking: The ability to design lesson plans in a visual and interesting way.

3. Information and communication technologies (ICT)

According to the 2026 educational standards, scientific and creative competence is inextricably linked with digital literacy:

Creating electronic educational resources (interactive games, video lessons).

Effective use of artificial intelligence capabilities in the educational process (for example, in optimizing the lesson plan).

4. Independent learning and reflective skills

A teacher should not stop working on himself:

Reflection: Critically analyze his own work and look for new ways to eliminate shortcomings.

International experience: Learning to prepare lesson plans that meet the requirements of international assessment programs such as PISA and PIRLS. At the first stage, within the framework of the value-motivational component, the manifestation of primary interest in scientific and creative activity as a value; within the framework of the cognitive-constructive component, the attempt to build new knowledge and transform information in content and meaning will be the result of the development of the scientific and creative competence of the primary school teacher in independent educational activities. Within the framework of the reflexive-purposeful component, professional difficulties in achieving the goal are identified. The goal of the second - constructive - stage is to develop the scientific and creative cognitive activity of future primary school teachers.

The master teacher will conduct a planned demonstration lesson, self-analysis, and invite teachers to participate in the "Master Class +" project, which consists of searching for scientific and creative ideas for development on such a topic, using the master teacher's ideas and their own.

• In the second stage, research methods are mainly applied, such as practical methods that provide deeper knowledge about the essence and characteristics of subjects, establish cause-and-effect relationships, organize the work of the creative participants' thoughts, and are implemented

through partial-search and project-research activities, and observation, experimentation, exercises, and scientific and creative work serve as sources of information. In the second stage, a non-standard approach to the educational process is developed, which is properly organized and produces high-quality results. The content of the second stage is based on the joint scientific and creative activity of teachers and workshop participants, and the result of this activity is the selection of forms, methods and means of organizing educational activities that correspond to a new topic or goal in a new master class or lesson project, and the prediction of the final results. The work of the creative team involves qualitative changes in the job system, which can lead to a qualitative change in the process and results of the future primary school teacher's activities. This situation indicates the priority of instructional (demonstrative)-practical, explanatory-conversational methods. Instead of ready-made examples of knowledge, information independently selected and processed in the process of working on the topic of the master class is used as a source of new knowledge.

CONCLUSION. As a result of improving the methodology for developing the scientific and creative competencies of future primary school teachers, their other activities will also improve. It should be noted that the development of scientific and creative competencies is a gradual and continuous process. It begins in a higher educational institution and continues in the workplace. In forming an individual style of pedagogical activity, each higher education teacher can choose for himself any heuristic forms and methods of teaching students. At the same time, the results of their application should ensure that they have a positive impact on the development of professional competencies of future primary school teachers based on scientific and creative approaches.

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